

THE EFFECTS OF TARDINESS TO THE ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF THE FCIC FIRST-YEAR COLLEGE STUDENTS ENROLLED IN A.Y. 2022-2023

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THE EFFECTS OF TARDINESS TO THE ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF THE FCIC FIRST-YEAR COLLEGE STUDENTS ENROLLED IN A.Y. 2022-2023

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ABSTRACT

Many problems can affect the academic performance of the students. One of these is tardiness. It can widely affect the academic performance of the students because of missed classes or instructional hours of learning. It may cause failed accomplishments in homework, written exams, and projects. It may become a habit of some students that may lead them to more serious problems like the poor learning process. A quantitative method was used in the study. The study was conducted in Franciscan College of the Immaculate Conception. Using a correlative research design, this study assessed the effects of tardiness on the academic performance of FCIC 1st first year college students. There were some identified factors causing tardiness: distance between residence to school, availability of transportation, sleeping late, waking up late, peer influence, laziness, traffic, household chores, health issues, financial problems, being a student parent and using gadgets. There were four identified effects to be affected by students' tardiness such as student's grade, academic output, being not attentive and miss important announcements / instructions in class. Data were collected by distributing questionnaires to 194 first year college students through purposive sampling. The data were analyzed using statistical method specifically the frequency distribution, mean and or percentage. The results of the study revealed that tardiness affects the academic performance of the FCIC 1st year college student especially with their grades. The results revealed that distance between residence to school are the most common factor of tardiness. This study adds body of knowledge and benefits of the educators, instructors, and students on the problem of tardiness of students for their teaching and learning.

Keywords: *Tardiness, Academic Performance, Students' Attendance*

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INTRODUCTION

Tardiness has been a serious matter for the students' academic performance. According to Merriam-Webster, tardiness is defined as the quantity or state of being late. The long man English Dictionary by A. W. Frisby defines lateness as after the proper time according to the world book dictionary by C. L. and R.K Barahat" lateness is defined as happening, coming of developing after the usual or proper time and lateness is also defined as a latecomer, as a person or group of people that arrive late. According to Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary defines lateness as being after the usual right or expected time, lateness as arriving after the expected time as expressed briefly this defines lateness as being late due to various reasons. One of those is they will make it habit. When students arrive late in the class, it can affect the flow of a discussion or in otherwise the class will be distracted.

Students who arrive late or tardy may failed from the beginning lecture, especially in morning class. For some teachers, attendance is a must, they may check the attendance if you are present or not before the discussion begin. To students the student who are always arrive late or frequently tardy may affect to their academic performance in terms of grades. This situation is very common to students and for the schools, the schools could do all to lessen this kind of problems such as performing in front of the class alone if you are late more than 15 minutes but it seems like it is still not noticeable.

Academic performance is the extent to which a student, teacher, or institution has attained their short or long-term educational goal and is measured either by continuous assessment or cumulative grade point average. If the students will make arrive late in class or if they will make it a habit it may cause missed compliance in assignments, projects, quizzes and etc. Several studies have shown that school tardiness has a negative impact on learning outcomes (Rebecca Vukonic 2017). It could reflect what you have done in the whole year's classes, through a report card. It will show if the students have passed or failed the school year they have attended. Academic performance is one way to identify if the student was active in class or not. It is also the way to identify the student if they excel.

Schools have rules on tardiness or absences. Tardiness is a serious matter but has no immediate consequences so the students lead to achieving poor performances in academics. Students are human, and teenagers can be a trial as much to their teachers as to their parents. Many students may be rude, absent, or late. Punctuality is important to each student in a way to get an average grade. This can be done by engaging various active performances like active performances such as role playing, reporting and other matters that engaging active performances.

Students nowadays have a problem managing their time when going to school. Tardiness is also one way of saying that a person is lazy or is not responsible to do things even with going to school early. In the Philippines, being late and starting things late has been part of Filipino culture. Many Filipinos seems to either practice it or accept it, so much that a term "Filipino Time" was coined (Tan, 2015). Tardiness is one of the main problems of students, which is why we conducted a study about tardiness and its effects to academic performance of first year college students of Franciscan College of the Immaculate Conception. The number of students who are late increased and also even during class time, where it is also the time where the other students arrive in school. That is why we want to know the different reasons on why things or scenarios like this happen. We conducted this study so that the students can be aware that being

late can affect their academic performance in school. We also want to know the reasons of being late, for us to help the students.

Therefore, this study aims to give an advice on how to be punctual to those students who are frequently inactive or being tardy in school and this aims to provide a discussion on the effects of tardiness of tardiness by solving the main problem and sub-problems presented in the statement of the problem. Hence, this study was conceptualized to determine the effects of tardiness on the academic performance of the FCIC first year college students enrolled in S.Y. 2022-2023.

Statement of the Problem

The content and discussion of this research paper will focus on the main problem and sub-problems that can be deduced from the topic. It will begin with an exposition of the various reasons for the tardiness of the students and how tardiness affects their academic performance. Thus, this paper will focus only to the questions below.

Main Problem:

What are the effects of tardiness on the academic performance of the first-year college students of FCIC?

Sub-problems:

1. Profile of respondents
2. How frequent do students become late in class?
3. How does tardiness affect the student academic performance?

Scope and Limitations

This study aims to find the causes and effects of lateness to students' academic performance and to determine in which of the factors causes their lateness.

This study examines, only the case of lateness of first-year college students of Franciscan College of Immaculate Conception Baybay City, Leyte. The researchers conducted through face-to-face and online survey using questionnaire to collect the needed data for the study. There was one instrument that was used in this study, which was the survey questionnaire having questions about reasons of being late, the effects of tardiness on their academic performance and the estimated range of GPA in the first semester of the first-year college students of FCIC enrolled in S.Y. 2022-2023.

Furthermore, this study was delimited to hypothesized effects of tardiness to the academic performance of the first-year college students of FCIC enrolled in S.Y. 2022-2023.

The Sample and Locale of the Study

The study will be conducted among the First Year College Students of the Franciscan College of the Immaculate Conception, one of the Catholic schools situated in Baybay City, Leyte. FCIC is a private, catholic basic and higher education institution managed by the Sisters of St. Francis of Perpetual Adoration in Baybay City, Leyte, Philippines. It was founded way back July 22, 1947 and is currently headed by Sister Mary Michael G. Bactong, OSF. The school offers and provides quality education which enables every student to develop various areas of knowledge that can help them in attaining success in the future and for them to become globally competitive.

To determine the effects of tardiness in academic performance of the students, the researchers will utilize non-probability sampling, specifically purposive method in selecting the respondents from the different programs of the First Year College students. The estimated total of students in first year college is 351. The researchers selected 194 students, who were qualified to be the respondents of the study.

TABLE 1. RESPONDENTS OF THE STUDY

PROGRAM	POPULATION	SAMPLE
EDUCATION	66	26
MIDWIFERY	36	29
CRIMINOLOGY	107	75
HOSPITALITY	60	36
MANAGEMENT		
BSBA	42	9
BSOA	16	10
IT	19	5
ACT	5	4
TOTAL NO. OF STUDENTS.	351	194

Instrumentation

In this study, the researchers will use questionnaires as the research instrument consisting of a series of questions and other prompts for the purpose of gathering information from respondents. Specifically, the researchers will use the structured questionnaires which entail questions with some control or questions that are short and limit the respondent to specific options. It is an instrument made by the researcher which will be used to gather data about the effects of tardiness on the academic performance of the FCIC first year college students.

In conducting the study, the researchers will determine the socio- demographic profile of the respondents which includes the respondents name, program, age, and sex. Aside from that, the researchers will also gather the reasons affecting students' tardiness. In addition, the researchers will determine how tardiness affect students' academic performance. The researcher will also determine their estimated average range during midterm and finals on the first semester to know the effect of tardiness on their academic performance. And this research tool is pilot tested to the second-year college students of FCIC.

Research Design

The researchers will utilize correlational type of research design which is defined as the research method that involves observing two variables in order to establish a statistically corresponding relationship between them. This method is to identify variables that have some sort of relationship do the extent that a change in one creates some change in the other. Specifically, this study uses purposive sampling because the researchers need only the respondents who said yes on the question "Are you a late comer?". Furthermore, the research design will help the researchers in collecting and analyzing the responses given by the respondents. Checklist and close-ended questions will be provided by the researchers in order to obtain their views, opinions, and perceptions on the subject.

The process of correlational research went beyond collection and tabulation of data. It involves gathering of large amounts of data in very little time. Thus, correlational research was often involved with determining the linear statistical relationship between two variables.

Gathering of Data

Upon the approval of research topic, the researchers will conduct the survey which contains about the effect of tardiness on the students' academic performance. The survey is essential to help the researchers in identifying the factors of tardiness and its effects on the academic performance of the students. In gathering the data, the researchers will distribute the questionnaires during the respondents' vacant time in order to avoid class disruption.

The respondents will be given enough time to answer each question and after gathering the data, the researchers will tally the scores and apply descriptive statistics specifically the percentage or average that will be used in analyzing the data.

As soon as the researchers gathered the data, the researchers will compile, sort, organize and tabulate the gathered data. The data are subject to statistical treatment in order to answer the questions proposed in the study. The statistical tools employed were frequency distribution, percentage and weighted mean.

In gathering the needed data, the researchers used this formula to get the percentage or the result of the tabulation:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Percentage} &= \% \\ \text{Frequency of category} &= f \\ \text{Total number of respondents} &= N \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Percentage} = \frac{\text{frequency of category}}{\text{Total number of respondents}} \times 100$$

$$\% = f/N \times 100$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Graph 1. Respondents of Sex Reference

The figure shows the dominating respondents of the study. Wherein, there are 99 respondents of the study are female and 95 respondents are male. Thus, based on the data we gathered uttermost of our respondents are female which has a 51.04%. According to Olowoyo (2021), a late coming of female learners hinged to a large degree on domestic factors while the late coming of male learners depended on attitude and peer pressure. The male learners were reluctant to change the habit as it was not perceived to be an emotional disturbance while female learners were amenable to habit change.

Graph 2. Respondents Age Reference

The graph shows the different age of the respondents. Wherein, the graph shows that the highest percentage of age scale is 18-24 which has a 89.18%. thus, based on the data we gathered the uttermost of our respondents are in the 18-24 ages. Most of the respondents are in aged 18-24 years old which mean that it falls within the normal range of a college student in the Philippines Educational System.

Graph 3. Late Comers of 1st Year College Students

This graph identified as who are the late comers of 1st year college students. Wherein, the graph shows that out of 351 first year college students, 194 says YES while 157 says NO. Thus, based on the data we gathered 55.27% student are late comer in the 1st year college of Franciscan College of the Immaculate Conception. Based on Kearny's continuum, tardiness is an imaginary part of a behavior that can be develop into school absenteeism, which in turn increases the risk of dropping out, school failure, long-lasting associations with crime, and problematic health behavior.

Graph 4. Times of Getting Late to School

This graph shows the number of times they came late at school weekly. Wherein, the graph shows that the 3 to 5 got the highest percentage which has a 37.63%. Thus, based on the data we gathered most of the student from 1st year college in FCIC came late at school 3-5 times per week. The National for Statistics indicates that student tardiness occurs at a rate of 3.3% to 9.5% each day for all students in kindergarten through grade twelve (Harrman, 2007). It is clear from literature that tardiness is a major problem.

Graph 5. Factors of Students Tardiness

The graph shows the factors of student tardiness. Wherein, the graph shows that the highest percentage of factors of students' tardiness is distance between residence and school which has the percent of 20% while the least factors are health issues and peer influence. Thus, based on the data we gathered the uttermost factor that experience by student tardiness in FCIC is distance between residence and school. According to the study of Dhald Lukman (2021), there are many factors that could make a student get late or develop the habit of getting late to school. This could be range from sleeping late, poor preparation, school factor, illness, engagement in too many house chores, school location and etc. that culminate into student arriving school late. Santillano (2010) stated that psychological theorist considered some "personality traits, including low self-esteem and anxiety. Some theorist considered tardiness on "inborn quality" since our being early or late is "partially biologically determined" which she also agreed, other expert also believed that some people are "chronically tardy" for the reason that they consciously and unconsciously get good things from it.

Table 2. Does Tardiness Affect Academic Performance

PROGRAM	YES	NO
EDUCATION	26	0
MIDWIFERY	26	3
CRIMINOLOGY	68	7
HOSPITALITY	30	6
MANAGEMENT		
BSBA	9	0
BSOA	10	0
IT	4	1
ACT	3	1
TOTAL NO. OF STUDENTS.	176	18

The table identified as does tardiness affect the students' academic performance. Wherein, the table shows that with the 194 respondents 176 said YES while 18 respondents answered NO. Thus, based on the data we gathered most of the students of 1st year college of FCIC, academic performance was affected by tardiness. Chronic tardiness is the act of repetitive late arrival that can give negative impact for the students especially in the academic performance (Maria Airth, August 20). According to Athlos (2018) students who are

chronically tardy perform worse on their academic performance such as worse test scores, academic activities, and morning huddles. According to Paul Caldarella et al. (2011) the principals and teachers acknowledge the student tardiness to be a serious issue as they miss important announcements or academic activities.

Graph 6. Effects of Tardiness in Student's Academic Performance

The graph shows the effect of tardiness on academic performance. Wherein, the graph shows that make your grade lower got the highest percentage which is 50.52%. Thus, based on the data we gathered the uttermost effect of tardiness on academic performance to the students in 1st year college is making your grade lower. According to Paul Caldarella et al. (2011) arriving late to school can also mean that students miss out on activities designed to build connections with their peers, potentially impacting their social interactions with and creating a greater sense of alienation from their classmates. Being late to the class may have impact to their subjects because they might miss the flow of lectures, record of some quizzes and activities to the respective subjects (Gile and Quinn Azzy Dy, 2018).

Graph 7. Students Grade from Midterm in the First Semester

The graph shows the grades from midterm in the first semester. Wherein, it shows that the grade scale 1.6-2.0 got the highest percentage which has a 54.12%. Thus, based on the data we gathered most of our respondents' grade are in 1.6-2.0 scale. According to Ballotpedia, academic performance is the measurement of student achievement across various academic subjects. Teachers and education officials typically measure achievement using classroom performance, graduation rates, and from standardized tests.

Graph 8. Students Grade from Finals in the First Semester

The graph shows the grades from final in the first semester. Wherein, it shows that the highest percentage grade scale was 1.6-2.0 which has a 54.12%. Thus, based on the data we gathered most of our respondents' grade are in the scale of 1.6-2.0 from final. Based from the previous graph which is the grades from midterm in first semester, we can say that they have same number of percentages in a grade scale 1.6-2.0 which has a 54.12%. However, as we compared the two data it has a change of grades from midterm to final. As we gathered the data, students' grade from midterm to final decreases. We observed that the two data, the grade scale 1.0-1.5, 1.6-2.0, and 2.6-3.0 has a change according to the data we gathered from midterm to final. The grade scale 1.6-2.0 in midterm to final have same percentage just a coincidence. One's tardiness, most especially a student might result to low academic performance for he or she has missed a part of the discussion (Maria Airth August 20). According to Nakpodia and Dafiaghor causes of tardiness will lead to low performance in school and even mental problems and problems in his/her study.

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Summary of Findings

The research is titled “The Effects of Tardiness on the Academic Performance of the FCIC First Year College Students”. The study was conducted in Franciscan College of the Immaculate Conception, Baybay City, Leyte. There were 194 first year college students who served as the respondents of the study.

The main purpose was to determine the effects of tardiness on the academic performance of the FCIC 1st year college student. Specifically, the study would like to know the factors of tardiness and how tardiness affects student’s academic performance. Additionally, the study wants to know the general weighted average (GWA) of the students in midterm and finals in the first semester to determine the effect of tardiness. Also, the study also aimed to determine the socio- demographic profile of the respondents (in terms of age, sex, program & year, and their address).

A correlative type of research design specifically, purposive sampling was used as a tool in gathering data and it was conducted in the aforementioned school. A survey questionnaire was used for 351 first year college students in different programs to determine the qualified respondents.

Results of the study revealed that most of the respondents were from the age 18-24 years old. Female are the most respondents in the study. It was also determined that most of the respondents said that they are late comers and most of them said that they came late at school 3-5 times a week.

It was also found out that through close-ended questionnaires, tardiness has some effects on the academic performance of the students. Illustrating that there are 50.52% response that tardiness makes grades lower, 20.62% response that missed important announcements / instructions in class, 20.10% response that lack of academic output, and 8.76% response that being not attentive in class. Additionally, with the data analyzed, it was determined that tardiness of students have some factors. Specifically, the most factor is the distance between residence and school, followed by doing chores/ helping at home, availability of transportation, sleeping late, using cellphones or gadgets, waking up late, financial problems, traffic, laziness, being a student parent, peer influence, health issues and others according to the data that we gathered. Moreover, the grades also of the students was found out from the midterm and finals in the first semester. The data shows that their grades in finals is different from the previous one, or showing that their grades became low.

Conclusion

The following conclusion are drawn from the study:

Most of our respondents are female which means that female students from first year college are experiencing uttermost tardiness than male. Most of the respondents are in aged 18-24 years old which mean that it falls within the normal range of a college student in the Philippines Educational System.

From the data we gathered and analyzed through pie graph bases in the components in the problem and objectives of the study, from the population of first year college students, 194 are identified as a latecomer which has the percentage of 55.27% while 157 students aren't. Most of our respondents experience 3-5 times late at school weekly with the percentage of 37.63%. The uttermost factor that have been experience by first year college was distance between residence to school with the percentage of 19.59% while the least factor that they experience was health issues and peer influence which has a 1.55%. It can be seen in the result that the respondents experience struggle towards tardiness due to the distance between residence and school. From the data we gathered, 90.72% of respondents' response YES on does tardiness affect their academic performance while 9.28% said NO. Hence, based on the result, most of our respondents say YES, which indicate that being tardy in school has a big impact on the academic performance of the students.

Scale grades data given from midterm in the 1st semester tells that most of the respondents' grade are in 1.6-2.0 with percent of 54.12%, followed by the grade scale 2.1 - 2.5 which has a 27.32% and then the grade scale 1.0-1.5 with the percentage of 12.37% and lastly the scale 2.6-3.0 which has a 6.19%. Scale grades data given from final in the 1st semester tells that most of the respondents' grade are in 1.6-2.0 with percent of 54.12% followed by the grade scale 2.1 - 2.5 which has a 32.47% and then the grade scale 1.0-1.5 with the percentage of 7.22% and lastly the scale 2.6-3.0 which has a 6.19%. The uttermost effect that have been experience by our respondents was make your grades lower which has the percentage of 50.52%, while the least effect they experience was being not attentive in class which has a 8.76%. Thus, based on the data we gathered; it can be seen in the result that tardiness of the student has an impact on their academic performance. Being tardy of the student will result of having low grades on each of their course.

Recommendation

1. The research suggests that intervention is required to combat student tardiness, to ensure guidelines are current and consequences for tardy behaviour is implemented and effective.

The report recommends a preventative school-wide plan include the following:

- active supervision of students in common areas during all transition periods
- clear definition and explicit teaching of expectations for behaviour during transition periods
- immediate and consistent consequences for tardiness

2. The research found that with the factors of student's greater risk of their tardiness to go to school. Therefore, it is recommended that students:

- Must set their time management in order to attend the class in time.
- Go to sleep earlier. Avoid using too much of cellphones and gadgets.
- Make your morning worth waking up for. Refresh your day with a habit of getting into class on time.

3. To the Future Researchers:

- You should not just limit your respondent to gather you data in order to have satiate information. Huge population of respondents is important so that you could obtain and achieve different and or various perspective, ideas, concepts, and or insights.
- Cite many citations to support the topic.
- Give more time to conduct the study thoroughly in order to answer the research problem.

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